

PARENTAL RESPONSIBILITY RIGHTS

Saidov Bakhodirkhoja Nasirkhojaevich

Email:bahodirxujasaidov@gmail.com

Security Department of the National Guard of the
Republic of Uzbekistan

Inspector of important assignments

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ABSTRACT

This article talks about the legal documents that need to be filled in the rights and responsibilities of parents that are relevant today, and the article shows that it is possible to increase the quality of education in educational institutions by increasing the responsibility towards children based on the current social views, and the current social consciousness. The solution to the problem, reducing the number of criminal cases at school age, increasing the responsibility of parents in preventing physical and mental violence, and strengthening the responsibility of parents.

INTRODUCTION

Relevance of the topic:"The more developed humanity is, the more it begins to live on the basis of multifaceted intangible interests, the more the multifaceted law is forced to protect them, in particular, civil law cannot avoid participating in this protection." [2]

One of the most urgent problems in new Uzbekistan is the protection of children's rights. The reason we say this is that today's underage children are in need of social protection, they are exposed to violence, and they are increasing in the world of crime. In this regard, the legislative chamber requires changes to be made to the outdated legal documents based on today's social life. experts from

different fields of science unanimously say that the family is losing its prestige and the traditional family foundations are weakening, "the collapse of the traditional, protective functions of the family or their opposite, decline It is definitely wrong to unanimously confirm that it will turn into a face. This makes it possible to connect the problem of implementing the protection of the rights and interests of minors to the global problems of our time, which the whole world community is interested in solving.

The full protection of children's rights remains relevant at the international level today: humanity cannot live without concern for future generations, because this issue essentially means concern for its

existence. offering appropriate legal solutions to students. As long as sufficient legal documents are not developed on the responsibility of parents, the number of children in need of social protection, entering the world of crime, moral backwardness, aimlessness and illiteracy will increase.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS FROM TOPIC SURFACE

Legal instruments have a special place in the system of measures to support children and protect their interests. Their range of child protection is very wide, but these measures are not always applied as they should be. More than 60 laws and other normative legal documents in various fields are directly or indirectly aimed at protecting children and their rights. [4]

Every child has the right to live in a family, to be brought up, to know his parents, to take care of them and to live with them. Children also have the right to be educated by their parents, to develop in all aspects, and to respect their human dignity.[5]

Most parents care for their children because they love them, try to bring them up well, inculcate various life skills and give them the best education.

At the same time, they perform the duties of parents based on the requirements of the law without knowing that this work is required by the law. Taking care of children is the constitutional duty of father and mother.[6]

- The obligations of parents are regulated by the Family Code, which explains the nature of the rights and obligations of parents in different life situations.

The state authorities of Uzbekistan pay great attention to the education of the young generation, but despite the

measures taken by the state, the issue of parents' responsibility and the importance of family values in their child's upbringing remains indifference.

So what are parental rights and parental responsibilities?

- The authority to take care of a child and make decisions affecting its well-being and proper development is called "parental responsibility".

What is parental responsibility? All mothers and most fathers have legal rights and responsibilities as parents - known as 'parental responsibilities'. If you have parental responsibility, your most important roles are to provide a home for the child, protect the child, and protect the child from harm. You are not responsible for: raising the child, choosing the child's education, consenting to the child's medical treatment, naming the child and consenting to any name change, taking care of the child's property. Parents have the right to parent their children. whether or not he has responsibility, he must ensure that he is financially supported. In addition, in accordance with the Law "On Education", the parents or other legal representatives of the students are responsible for the physical,

At the same time, parents must not only ensure that children receive a general education, but also ensure that they comply with the internal procedures of the school, the rules for children living in boarding schools, and the established requirements for the regime. [7]

The law also defines the obligations of parents to raise children. Therefore, the family is considered as a social institution, with the help of which children are taught not only the skills of interaction with other members of society, but also to observe

certain limits of behavior in society. Raising a child takes time, work, and it is not an easy task, but without it, the desired result cannot be achieved.

Another task that involves the provision of minor children by their parents is child support. This includes not only food and clothing, but also age-appropriate toys, treatment, recreation, and education.[8]

In addition, parents are obliged to support children until they reach the age of 18 or until the child is legally emancipated (from the age of 16).

METHODOLOGY

In this theoretical study, all electronic and written sources on the subject were studied, and the best practices of developed countries such as Japan were studied. In order to justify the relevance of the research question, the problems related to the responsibility of most parents were studied through the method of independent observation during my work.

RESULT DISCUSSION -Parental responsibility is the legal rights, obligations and powers over the child and his property. Therefore, the person with parental responsibility for the child has the right to make important decisions regarding the care and education of the child.

In this regard, let's briefly list the rights and responsibilities of parents provided in our legal documents:

Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan:

- Parents have the right and duty to educate their children.
- Parents are responsible for the upbringing and development of their children. They are obliged to take care of

their children's health, physical, mental, spiritual and moral development.

- Protecting the rights and interests of children is entrusted to their parents.
- Parents are the legal representatives of their children and protect their rights and interests in relations with individuals and legal entities, including in courts without special powers.
- Parents have the right to put their children above all other persons.
- Parents must provide for minor children.
- Parents have equal rights and equal responsibilities towards their children.
- Parents are not responsible for the obligations of the emancipated minor, in particular, the obligations resulting from harming them.

A person can be declared fully competent in the following cases:

- ▶ upon reaching the age of eighteen (majority);
- ▶ declaring a minor to be fully legal (emancipation);
- ▶ marriage of minors.

Parental rights are terminated when the children reach the age of eighteen (the majority).

Responsibility of parents of minors

Exercise of parental rights

- The right to communicate with the child of grandparents, brothers, sisters and other close relatives.
- Minor parents have the right to live with the child and take part in his upbringing.
- Unmarried minor parents have the right to independently exercise parental rights after the age of 16, in the event that a child is born to them and their motherhood and (or) paternity is established.

-Until the minor parents reach the age of 16, a guardian can be appointed for the child who will carry out his upbringing together with the minor parents of the child.

- Disputes arising between the child's guardian and minor parents are resolved by the guardianship and guardianship body.

- Parents of minors have the right to recognize and challenge their paternity and motherhood on a general basis. Parents have the right and duty to raise their children.

-Parents are responsible for the education and development of their children. They are obliged to take care of their children's health, physical, mental, spiritual and moral development.

- Parents have the right to put their children before all other persons.

-Parents are obliged to ensure the level of education of their children established by law. The protection of children's rights and interests is entrusted to their parents.

- Parents are the legal representatives of their children and protect their rights and interests in relations with physical and legal entities, including in courts without special powers.

-If the guardianship and guardianship body determines that there is a conflict between the interests of parents and children, parents do not have the right to protect the interests of their children.

- In case of disagreements between parents and children, the guardianship and patronage body is obliged to appoint a representative to protect the rights and interests of children.

In addition, there are rights related to separate parental responsibility for single-parent families.

Completion of parental responsibility rights and recommendations for additions to it

- Violence against children by parents, use of force, forced labor, physical, mental, and psychological violence against children, which are considered to be the result of current social stress.

- Taking into account the increasing number of large and small criminal cases of school-aged children, especially in the period of young adulthood, to include in the legislation the responsibility of parents for the moral views of education and upbringing of children.

- Development of the rules of internal order in educational relations, the relationship between students and teachers, and parental responsibility for behavior in public places.

- In addition, it is necessary to include parental responsibility for controlling the virtual life of minors who violate the conditions of correct use of social networks.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, it can be said that in improving the rights of parental responsibility, we should first of all study the experience of developed countries such as Japan, which currently has a special demand for parental responsibility, based on international experience. The decline in moral education of modern children, their daily pursuit of easy life and ignorance is the result of the indifference of today's parents. Today, if we do not remind parents of their responsibility, the visibility of the future generation's education will further decrease, and it will cause them to lose their national moral views. possibleAs the father knows the responsibility of the mother, he is ready to take responsibility

before the child is born, and he starts paying more attention to improving all economic and social conditions.

- In this regard, another reminder to parents: "Modern parents do not mean parents who work day and night, who earn more money for their children and pay all

the necessary conditions for their financial comfort, but parents who take time off from all their work for the science of raising their children." Dear parents, know that your responsibility to your child is your responsibility to society and the state. (BS Nasirhojaevich)

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